

SURVEILLANCE CARD_CCHF_Serological surveillance of domestic ruminants in high-risk areas

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Serological surveillance of domestic ruminants in high-risk areas.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread to new areas. Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen.
3	Target species and group	Cattle, sheep and goats, adult life animals with potential exposure to ticks (on pasture or in outdoor areas without a tick control programme).
4	Target sector / production type	All production types where animals are raised outdoors (and no tick control programme is applied).
5	Geographical area covered	High-risk areas with regards to introduction of disease (close to endemic areas) and presence of ticks (climate, vegetation). Areas with suspected presence of CCHF or which have previously been endemic to CCHF.
6	Age group	Adult animals.
7	Sampling point and strategy	On farm, random two-stage sampling of farms and animals within farms.
8	Sampling time period	Vector period (spring to autumn).
9	Sampling matrix	Blood serum.
10	Type of disease indicators	Presence of antibodies.
11	Sampling unit	Animals and herds.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Random sampling of all herds with potential exposure to ticks within high-risk areas. The survey can be designed as well for demonstrating disease freedom.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Indirect immunofluorescence test or ELISA. Pooling of samples from the same herd is possible, but currently no information on sensitivity of tests on pooled samples is available. Standardization of serological test is needed, because currently no method is accepted as gold standard methodology.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined by country.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined by country, ideally 95% confidence.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	<p>This activity targets a known population, and the sensitivity of detection can be calculated if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample, which can be achieved by different sampling strategies, including for instance random, stratified, or risk-based. Estimation of the sensitivity in the latter case depends on proper definition of the risk strata and their relative risks.</p> <p>The sensitivity of the component can be calculated and used to estimate an overall sensitivity of the system combined with other components.</p>
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	<p>Q-Fever serology.</p> <p>Could be combined with surveys to demonstrate freedom from disease (<i>Brucella melitensis</i> in small ruminants / Enzootic Bovine Leucosis and Infectious Bovine Rhinotracheitis in cattle). However, these surveys do not require seasonal sampling and do not target animals exposed to ticks.</p>
18	References	<p>1) Cicculi V, Maitre A, Ayhan N, Mondoloni S, Paoli JC, Vial L, de Lamballerie XN, Charrel R, Falchi A. Lack of Evidence for Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus in Ticks Collected from Animals, Corsica, France. <i>Emerg Infect Dis.</i> 2022 May;28(5):1035-1038. doi: 10.3201/eid2805.211996. PMID: 35447051; PMCID: PMC9045455.</p>

		2) Mazzola LT, Kelly-Cirino C. Diagnostic tests for Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever: a widespread tickborne disease. <i>BMJ Glob Health</i> . 2019 Feb 20;4(Suppl 2):e001114. doi: 10.1136/bmjgh-2018-001114. PMID: 30899574; PMCID: PMC6407549.
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